
GST About Electric Vehicle- A Medium Towards Green Initiatives

Monali Sachin Battise¹ & Yogita Pandurang Chaudhari²

¹Dyansadhna Degree College, Thane

²North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon

Corresponding Author – Monali Sachin Battise

DOI -10.5281/zenodo.15501813

Abstract:

This paper shows that the GST department also taking Green Initiatives by reducing GST rate on Electric Vehicles, it shows how they are showing their participation for a good environment movement and also it shows how the consumers shows their interest and do duty for a good environment. The analytical review shows the conclusion for green initiative as per the consumers that they showing positive response for the decision of GST department going correctly by reducing the rate of GST on it.

Keywords: *GST, Green Initiatives, Electric Vehicle, Environment, Consumers, Correctly*

Introduction:

Green initiative means any activity takes to decrease the bad effect on environment. GST(Goods and Service Tax) department is also took a step for Green initiatives to reduce or decrease the bad impact on environment i.e. they reduce the GST rate on Electric vehicle. Electric vehicle helps to environment by reducing air pollution. In other words, Goods and Service Tax (GST) is levied on the supply of goods and services. Goods and Services Tax Law in India is a comprehensive, multi-stage, destination-based tax that is levied on every value addition. After subsuming majority indirect taxes, GST is a single domestic indirect tax law for the entire country. The two-wheeler market has been made affordable, and this has driven manufacturers and consumers to electrify. High fuel costs also encourage shifting to greener alternatives furthering this best initiative.

Objectives:

1. To show that the nation actually moving towards green initiatives with GST decisions
2. To understand the influence of green initiatives
3. To understand the consumers behavior in choice of product
4. To identify the adoption for the green initiative

Research Methodology:

Primary data: The research is done through observation method and collection of data through questionnaires with Google Form.

Secondary Data: Secondary data is collected from internet websites and Wikipedia to develop the theory.

Sample Size: The sample size is determined as 62 respondent's opinion from the consumers.

Analytical Review:

1. Distribution as per Gender wise:

Gender	Total
Male	39
Female	23
Total	62

2. Distribution as per “Awareness about Green Initiative”

Awareness About Green Initiative	Total
Yes	62
No	0
Total	62

3. Distribution as per “Choice of Product”

Choice of Product	TOTAL
Electric vehicle	56
Non- electric vehicle	6
TOTAL	62

4. Distribution as per “Opinion about Govt. declaration for reduction in GST for Electric Vehicle for Green Initiative Program”

Opinion about Govt. declaration for reduction in GST for Electric Vehicle for Green Initiative Program	
Strongly Agree	36
Agree	25
Neutral	0
Disagree	0
Strongly Disagree	1
TOTAL	62

5. Distribution as per “Opinion of preference for buying Electric vehicle”

Opinion of preference for buying Electric vehicle	
Strongly Agree	30
Agree	25
Neutrel	5
Disagree	1
Strongly Disagree	1
TOTAL	62

Advantages:

GST prevents the cascading influence of tax. In the retail sector, GST simplifies tax procedures and facilitates compliance. Retailers claim input tax credits, improving financial viability. In addition, GST promotes market expansion by eliminating barriers to interstate trade, empowering retailers to explore new territories and opportunities for growth. GST department declare to reduce rate of GST on Electric Vehicle from 12% to 5% for financial year 2025-26 and this declaration impacted on retailers to increase their sales of Electric vehicle by also increased in demand rate by consumers. By this announcement they also provide other beneficial facilities to retailers as well as to consumers. The electric vehicles helps to lowering carbon footprints, lowering maintenance costs, sustainable charging, energy conservation, lowering running costs, improving air quality, lesser air and noise pollution and so on, and the retailers becomes a part of this help to environment. Because this is a environment friendly the demand for this is more and this demand helps to retailers to increase their sales as compare to other vehicle sales. As compare to other vehicles they also get a high margin of profit.

Limitations:

This study is limited to Thane city only.

Conclusion:

From the above study it shown that the nation is actually moving to green initiatives with the participation of GST department as well as participation of consumers. The above shown statistical data prove that the decision of GST department has going correctly and in these decision consumers showing their positive response. Here maximum consumers are prefer to buy and use electric vehicle for taking part in green initiatives.

References:

1. <https://www.mygstrefund.com/gst-on-evs-impact-benefits/>
2. <https://cleartax.in/s/gst-law-goods-and-services-tax>
3. <https://evreporter.com/maharashtra-ev-sales-trend-jan-2022-to-sep-2022/>
4. <https://energy.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/power/all-you-need-to-know-about-the-gst-on-evs/116668146>
5. <https://www.ndtv.com/business-news/gst-council-increases-tax-on-used-ev-car-sale-by-business-7305123>